

Higher Education Ranking **HERanking**

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Higher Education Ranking and evaluations is one of the main pillars that are relied on during the development process of universities, higher education institutions, research centers, scientific and research institutes, and all institutions that carry the "prospect" of higher education institution regardless of their name (university - institute - college - school - academia) in which, the label is loose and does not carry a specific and a determined measure. Generally speaking, the ranking of Higher Education Institutions HEIs is based on several criteria on which the university depends in its work and performs calculations that ultimately lead to a numerical value that is calculated, compared and equated with the values of other universities. This value is compared among local, regional and international universities. [Ranking](#) of Higher Education Institutions is of great importance as the universities depend on it to measure its progress or decrease it by adopting the criteria set by the academic classification bodies and in Europe in particular, ranking of universities is of great importance and it is being taken into account by students during admission process. Ranking agencies are committed to integrity and transparency during their evaluation of the ranking of institutions of higher education. The whole process is carried out automatically without any manual intervention. Transparency is one of the most important and influential factors.

Today, in 2019, there are 18 international rating agencies that rank universities worldwide and a number of other local ranking agencies that depend on the

ranking of universities in a single country. All of these bodies are licensed by the [IREG Observatory on Academic Ranking and Excellence](#), the official entity in the licensing of academic ranking agencies. Each ranking body relies on specific criteria in its work and encourages all institutions of higher education to demonstrate their electronic presence and publish all their activities on the Internet. For rankings based on web-content criteria's, there are three rankings worldwide, and Higher Education Ranking [HERanking](#) is the fourth in the world in its work mechanism. It is very important to note that the Ranking of Universities is not seen as a tool to encourage institutions of higher education to develop their work in the areas covered and measured, but rather to stimulate universities to develop their work at all levels and scientific and research fields, support the spread and external presence and promote the principle of joint action and building relationships and partnerships between all institutions of higher education around the world, and to build bridges of cooperation and joint action among all these institutions.

Links:

www.heranking.com